

ECONOMIC ANALYSIS OF CUSTARD APPLE PRODUCTION UNDER THE DIRECT SELLING AND SALE AFTER PROCESSING: A COMPARATIVE STUDY

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Abstract:

The present study conducted at Patur tahasil of the Akola district of Vidarbha region of Maharashtra state with the objective to undertake the study of value addition of custard apple as well as economic analysis of custard apple through direct sale. For this study, 20 respondents were selected by using random sampling method and one respondent were selected from the Amravati district irrespective of the tahasil were selected as respondents for the study of value addition of custard apple and data was collected by personal interview method. The findings of the study revealed that, the B:C ratio of value addition in custard apple (i.e., pulp extraction) was 2.63 and direct sale in the market (cost of cultivation) was 1.85. It demonstrates that, value addition in custard apples generated more profit than direct market selling.

Key words- Custard apple and Value addition.

Introduction:

About 38 per cent of the world population lives in dryland and farming in dryland agriculture is a challenging task, frequent drought and unseasonal rainfall disturbs farming. In Maharashtra, 33 per cent of the total area is affected due to unseasonal rainfall, which approximately affected 103.52 lakh farmers. In this manner, the Custard apple (*Annona squamosa L.*) is an important dryland fruit crop which belongs to family annonaceae. Custard apple occupies more area than any other species of annona. It is proving boon to the arid zones of Maharashtra because of their wider adaptability, comparatively freeness from pests and diseases, hardy nature, known to thrive under diverse soil and climatic conditions and also escape from grazing animals. The custard apple is used by indigenous as an insecticidal and antitumor agent, anti-diabetic, antioxidant, anti-epidemic, and anti-inflammatory agent which may be characterized due to the presence of the cyclic peptides. Area under custard apple cultivation in Vidarbha region of Maharashtra is 10367.00 ha. with 70945 MT productivity and the average production is 6.88 MT per hectare in Vidarbha (Anonymous, 2020). The Vidarbha region of Maharashtra is mostly characterised by dryland farming, and it's expected to have a serious economic and social impact on Vidarbha, particularly on rural farmers whose livelihood depends largely on rainfall. From a commercial point of view, there are limited dryland fruit crops available in the Vidarbha region and custard apple has become the best alternative for the dryland farmers because this crop requires less water as compared to major traditional fruit crops. From the available data, it has been observed that areas under custard apple are steadily increasing. As a result, in order to improve economic returns, it is necessary to promote custard apple farming in the Vidarbha region among dryland farmers.

Custard apple is a dry-land fruit crop that is well suited to Vidarbha's low rainfall areas. Considering the increasing area and future opportunities under this fruit crop as well as the non-availability of

storage facilities, farmers do not have any option other than processing. As a result, the current study attempts to determine, from an economic standpoint, whether this fruits will be suitable for direct sale or sale after processing. For this purpose, the study of value addition in custard apples (i.e. sale after processing) has been undertaken irrespective of the selected respondent.

Material and Method:

Economics analysis of value addition in custard apple

It reflected the difference between price for which a firm sold its product and the cost incurred on the purchased inputs by it. This difference represented the value addition by the productive activities of the firm.

Value addition = Selling price of the product – Cost of the total inputs.

In this study cost-A was calculated, and its components include (i) required raw materials, (ii) packing materials, (iii) human labour costs, (iv) electricity and water charges, (v) taxes, and (vi) interest working capital. Another one is cost-B, i.e., fixed cost, which includes interest on fixed cost-plus depreciation cost.

The data was collected from a single farmer who was engaged in value addition of custard apple. The collected information regarding value addition has been analyzed and the economics are presented in Table 1.

It shows from Table 1 that the total cost incurred for the preparation of 140 kg of custard apple pulp was Rs. 14,030.00 out of this. The variable cost contribution was extremely high, at 96.96 per cent.

The total income from custard apple pulp and by-product obtained was Rs. 36950.00, and the net return obtained was Rs. 22,920.00. The input-output ratio of 2.63 was found to be double and it is economically significant.

The result is limited to the machine's per-day capacity. Suppose, the respondent runs their machine throughout the season (i.e., 45 to 60 days) then net returns will increase according to the capacity of the pulp extraction machine.

Table 1 Economic analysis of custard apple value addition

Sr. No	Particulars	Unit	Quantity	Average rate (Rs)	Cost (Rs)	Per cent to Total
A) Variable cost						
I	Raw Material					
a.	Custard apple fruits	Kg /day	400.00	18.00	7200.00	51.32
II	Packing					
a.	Polythene bags	nos.	35.00	2.00	70.00	0.50
III	Labour cost					
a.	Male	nos./day	4.00	350.00	1400.00	
b.	Female	nos./day	15.00	300.00	4500.00	
IV	Total Labour Cost				5900.00	42.05
a	Electricity and water	Unit / day	22.00	17.00	374.00	2.67
b	Taxes				60.00	0.43

c	Interest on working Capital @6%				816.24	5.82
	Variable cost				13604.00	96.96
	Variable cost per kg				34.01	
B) Fixed Cost						
a.	Interest on fixed cost @10%				248.00	1.77
b.	Depreciation				178.00	1.27
	Total Fixed Cost				426.00	3.04
Total cost (A+B)					14030.00	100.00
Returns						
a.	Quantity (Custard Apple Pulp)	kg	140	250	35000.00	
b.	Byproduct (Seed)	kg	30	65	1950.00	
c.	Total Return				36950.00	
d.	Net Returns				22920.00	
Input output Ratio					2.63	

Economic analysis of custard apple through direct sale

The estimation of costs helps us to know the profitability of crop enterprises. The standard cost concept was used to calculate the per hectare cost of custard apple cultivation as follows:

Cost-A was estimated with for custard apple cultivation of total working capital plus interest on working capital plus depreciation in farm implements and farm buildings plus land revenue and other taxes. Working cost includes 15 sub costs like (i) Hired human labour wages (male and female), (ii) Bullock labour wages, (iii) Hired machinery charges, (iv) cost of manures (v) Cost of fertilizers, (vi) Irrigation charges, (vii) Plant protection, (viii) Incidental charges, (ix) Repairing charges, (x) Interest on working capital, (xi) Depreciation cost, (xii) Land revenue cess & other taxes, (xiii) Establishment cost (xiv) Rental value of land (xv) Interest on fix capital (xvi) Family human labour.

Cost-'B' was calculated by adding the interest on fixed capital @10 per cent per annum and rental value of owned land @ 1/6th of gross produce to cost 'A'.

Cost-'C' is the total cost of production which included the entire cost item, actual as well as imputed. The imputed value of own family labour is to be imputed and added to cost 'B' to work out cost 'C'
Cost 'C' = Cost 'B' + imputed value of family labours

The data was collected from 20 custard apple growers from the Akola district of Vidarbha region of Maharashtra state were analyzed and their economics are presented in Table 2.

It is observed from Table 2 that the per hectare cost of cultivation, i.e. Cost 'C' was Rs. 162232.49. Among the different items of expenditure, rental value of land accounted for the highest (24.49%), share in total cost 'C' followed by hired human labour (14.30%), manures (6.96%), establishment cost (5.75%) and family human labour (2.43%). Followed by fertilizers' (3.94%) share of the total cost. The per hectare yield obtained by the farmer was 116.20 quintals.

Table 2 Per hectare cost of cultivation of custard apple (Rs/ha)

Sr.No.	Particulars	Unit	Input	Cost/Input (Rs.)	Total Cost (Rs)	Percent to total cost "C"
1	Hired human labour					
	Male	days	47.19	297.60	14043.74	8.66
	Female	days	37.73	242.65	9155.18	5.64
	Total Labour Cost		84.92		23198.93	14.30
2	Bullock labour	(pair /days)	6.27	403.51	2530.01	43.26
3	Machine charges	Hours	3.55	355.67	1262.63	0.78
4	Manures	Qt.	12.75	885.78	11293.70	6.96
5	Fertilizers (N)	Kg	91.73	25.40	2329.94	1.44
	(P)	Kg	59.65	34.25	2043.01	1.26
	(K)	Kg	53.99	37.28	2012.75	1.24
6	Irrigation charges	Rs			1085.72	0.67
7	Plant protection	Rs			1378.45	0.85
8	Incidental charges	Rs			235.46	0.15
9	Repairing charges	Rs			276.85	0.17
	Working capitals (1 to 9)	Rs			47647.44	29.37
10	Interest on working Capital @6%	Rs			2858.85	1.76
11	Depreciation	Rs.			371.55	6.35
12	Land Rev. Cess & other taxes	Rs.			159.45	0.10
	Cost 'A'				51037.29	31.46
13	Establishment cost	Rs.			9327.75	5.75
14	Rental value land	Rs.			39735.45	24.49
15	Int. on Fix Cap @10% / annum	Rs.			1764.85	1.09
	Cost 'B'				101865.34	62.79
16	Family human labour					
	Male	days	19.65	297.60	5847.84	1.27
	Female	days	14.35	242.65	3482.03	1.16

	Cost 'C'				9329.87	5.75
	Total of cost (A+B+C)				162232.49	100.00
Returns						
a.	Yield per Hectare	Qtl.	116.2	3975	461895	
B	Total Return				461895	
c	Net Returns				299662.51	
	Per quintal cost of production				1396.15	
	Input - output Ratio				1.85	

The total cost 'A' and the total cost 'B' incurred by the growers in the cultivation of custard apple were 31.46 per cent and 62.79 per cent respectively. Per quintal cost of production of custard apple was observed Rs.1396.15.

The total income from custard apple cultivation obtained was Rs. 46,1895 and the net return obtained was Rs. 29,966.21. The input-output ratio was found to be 1.85 which is economically significant. As per the observation recorded by the researcher, all twenty custard apple growers sold their fruits directly in the market through the commission agent or the middle man, resulting in a minimum return from direct selling as compared to the grading and packaging of fruits. If the respondents sell their fruit using a good marketing plan, the estimated result may be different.

Conclusion:

According to Tables 1 and 2, the B:C ratio of value addition in custard apple (i.e., pulp extraction) was 2.63 and direct sale in the market (cost of cultivation) was 1.85. It demonstrates that, value addition in custard apples generated more profit than direct market selling.

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